

Expectations, Issues, and Needs of Generation X and Generation Y Employees

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Abstract In the present day, the workforce is becoming more diverse, as numerous generations coexist. Generation X (born between 1965 and 1980) and Generation Y, or Millennials (born between 1981 and 1996), comprise substantial portions of this workforce. Organizations seeking to improve employee satisfaction, retention, and productivity must comprehend their unique expectations, concerns, and requirements. This paper offers a comprehensive examination of the characteristics, expectations, issues, and requirements of Generation X and Generation Y employees, which is substantiated by pertinent research and references.

Keywords Generation X, Generation Y, Employee Retention, Employee Satisfaction, Employee Needs and Expectations.

Introduction

Humans possess emotions, requirements, and anticipations. In accordance with the esteemed Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory (Maslow, 1987), an individual endeavours to satisfy their personal requirements in the order indicated by the theory. The resources available at the workplace facilitate the fulfillment of those requirements while employed (Balc, A., & Bozkurt, S., 2013). In the past, numerous studies have demonstrated that employees who are content exhibit high productivity and low turnover intentions. Consequently, it is imperative to comprehend the expectations and requirements of the existing personnel. In the existing situation, individuals who are employed are members of the X and Y generations. Gaining a more profound understanding of the characteristics of these generations will enable us to better comprehend their behavior and expectations.

Objective of study

To examine the expectations, issues and needs of the Generation X and Generation Y employees. This will help us to identify the areas in which organizations can work with the intention of providing better resources at work that can empower the employees. An empowered employee reciprocates at workplace through better performance and efforts put into delivering job responsibilities, as propounded by the Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964).

Review of Literature

This paper has been prepared on the basis of review of literature including articles, research papers, reports and other internet sources which were discussed through out the paper.

Main Text

I) Characteristics of Generation X and Generation Y

i) Generation X possess the following characteristics:

While they were still in their early years, members of Generation X, the generation that came after the Baby Boomers, were exposed to considerable societal differences. These shifts have resulted in the formation of their distinctive qualities:

1. Independence and Self-Reliance: Independence and resourcefulness are two characteristics that are commonly associated with Generation X. Numerous members of Generation X acquired the skills of self-sufficiency and adaptability as a result of their upbringing in an era marked by economic instability and high rates of divorce (McCrinkle, 2021). They have a comfortable relationship with technology, but they also have a healthy amount of skepticism regarding it. They strike a balance between their familiarity with technology and their careful approach to the potential consequences of it (Reisenwitz, T. H., & Iyer, R., 2009).

2. Balance Between Work and Life: This generation places a great priority on maintaining a healthy work-life balance. As a result of having seen their parents suffer with issues such as extended working hours and job uncertainty, members of Generation X are looking to steer clear of the same challenges. According to Twenge (2010), they place a high priority on flexible working arrangements and make it a point to establish a distinct differentiation between their personal and professional life.

3. Pragmatism and Skepticism: Members of Generation X have a tendency to be distrustful of institutions and people in positions of authority. The reasons for this cynicism stem from their personal experiences with downsizing in corporations, political scandals, and unstable economic conditions. According to Schroth (2019), as a consequence of this, they are realistic and frequently choose communication that is plain and honest.

ii) Generation Y possess the following characteristics:

Generation Y, also known as Millennials, came of age during a time when globalization and technological advancement were occurring at a rapid pace. The emergence of Generation Y in the global workforce has prompted businesses to reconsider their working practices and adapt their environments to accommodate these young employees and managers. Organizations recognize the importance of retaining Generation Y, who are known for their lack of loyalty to companies (Ling Lim, H., 2012). To reduce turnover, companies must find ways to engage Generation Y without showing favoritism compared to other generations in the workforce, and without incurring additional costs. Attracting and retaining Generation Y poses challenges for organizations, as these individuals seek a more stimulating and purposeful work environment. They value continuous feedback and believe in the benefits of mentoring for personal growth and development (Treuren, G., & Anderson, K., 2010). Included among their traits are:

1. Technology-friendly: Millennials are said to be digital natives since they have grown up with the internet, cellphones, and social media; therefore, they are proficient in technology. According to the Pew Research Center (2019), individuals' work habits, communication preferences, and expectations for digital tools and platforms are all influenced by their deep integration with technology.

2. Desire for Meaningful Work and Impact: Millennials place a high value on work that has a purpose and has an impact. They are inspired by the possibility of making a contribution to causes that are important to them, and they anticipate that their employers will share their beliefs and principles. According to Deloitte (2023), this generation is drawn to businesses that exhibit social responsibility and ethical business practices during their operations.

3. Preference for Collaborative Work and Feedback: Millennials flourish in environments that encourage open communication and teamwork, creating a climate that is conducive to collaboration. According to Gallup (2016), they like working environments that cultivate a sense of community and mutual support, and they look for opportunity to receive regular feedback and recognition for their achievements.

II) Expectations of Generation X and Generation Y Employees

i) Expectations of Generation X

1. Career Advancement: Generation X employees expect clear pathways for career advancement. They value opportunities to progress within their organizations and seek professional development programs that can enhance their skills and career prospects (McCrinkle, 2021). They are likely to be motivated by roles that offer opportunities for growth and increased responsibility.

2. Work-Life Balance: As previously mentioned, Generation X highly values work-life balance. They expect flexibility in their work schedules and appreciate options such as

telecommuting and flexible hours. This flexibility allows them to manage their professional and personal responsibilities more effectively (Twenge, 2010).

3. Job Security: Despite their independent nature, Generation X employees prioritize job security. They seek stability and reliable benefits from their employers, having experienced the instability of previous economic downturns and corporate restructuring (Schroth, 2019).

ii) Expectations of Generation Y

1. Purposeful Work: Millennials anticipate that their employment will be meaningful and consistent with their personal values. They are attracted to organizations that have a well-defined mission and make a positive impact on society. They are interested in employers who are dedicated to social and environmental causes and are willing to participate in initiatives that align with these values (Deloitte, 2023).

2. Autonomy and Flexibility: Millennials, like Generation X, prioritize autonomy in their employment arrangements. They favor organizations that provide them with the freedom to manage their work in a manner that aligns with their personal preferences and requirements, as well as those that provide remote work options (Pew Research Center, 2019).

3. Career Development: Millennials are enthusiastic about the prospect of ongoing learning and professional growth. They anticipate that their employers will offer opportunities for career advancement, mentorship, and training. This generation prioritizes feedback and pursues environments that enable them to develop new skills and advance their occupations (Gallup, 2016).

III) Issues Faced by Generation X and Generation Y Employees

i) Issues Faced by Generation X

1. Technological Adaptation: While Generation X is generally proficient with technology, they may struggle with the rapid pace of technological change. Adapting to new digital tools and platforms can be challenging, especially if they are not provided with adequate training and support (McCrinkle, 2021).

2. Career Stagnation: Some Generation X employees may face career plateaus, where they perceive limited opportunities for advancement within their current organizations. This stagnation can lead to dissatisfaction and a desire to seek new opportunities elsewhere (Schroth, 2019).

3. Work-Life Integration: Generation X employees frequently encounter difficulties in achieving work-life balance, despite their appreciation for it, as a result of the insufficient flexible work options and the demanding nature of their job responsibilities. Stress and exhaustion may result from this conflict between work obligations and personal life (Twenge, 2010).

ii) Issues Faced by Generation Y

1. High Expectations and Pressure: Millennials often set high expectations for themselves and their employers, which can lead to pressure and stress (Malik, S., & Khera, S. N., 2014). The desire for meaningful work and rapid career progression can contribute to feelings of inadequacy or burnout when these expectations are not met (Deloitte, 2023).

2. Financial Challenges: Many Millennials face significant financial pressures, including student loan debt and high living costs. These financial challenges can impact their job satisfaction and influence their career decisions, as they may prioritize financial stability over other job factors (Pew Research Center, 2019).

3. Job Hopping: Millennials are known for frequently changing jobs in pursuit of better opportunities and experiences. This tendency to job hop can pose challenges for employers in terms of retaining talent and maintaining continuity within teams (Gallup, 2016).

IV) The Requirements of Generation X and Generation Y Employees

i) Needs of Generation X

1. Professional Growth: Generation X employees require access to training and development opportunities that facilitate their career advancement and skill development. Programs that provide career advancement and skill-building resources should be prioritized by employers (McCrindle, 2021).

2. Flexible Work Arrangements: Generation X employees are provided with flexible work options, including remote work and adjustable hours, to accommodate their desire for work-life balance. These arrangements can assist them in more effectively managing their professional and personal obligations (Twenge, 2010).

3. Respect and Recognition: Generation X prioritizes respect for their experiences and recognition for their contributions. In order to cultivate a positive work environment, organizations should establish systems for recognizing their accomplishments and utilizing their expertise (Schroth, 2019).

ii) Needs of Generation Y

1. Purpose-Driven Work: Millennials require a sense of fulfillment that their work is in accordance with their personal values and contributes to a greater cause. Employers should engage Millennials in meaningful initiatives that reflect these values and communicate their commitment to social responsibility (Deloitte, 2023).

2. Career Development Opportunities: In order to facilitate their professional development, Generation Y employees necessitate ongoing career development and mentoring (Arora, N., & Dhole, V., 2019). Training programs, mentorship opportunities, and explicit career progression pathways ought to be implemented by organizations (Gallup, 2016).

3. Feedback and Communication: Millennials thrive on regular feedback and open communication. Organizations should establish systems for frequent performance reviews and create channels for transparent dialogue to meet their preference for continuous feedback and interaction (Pew Research Center, 2019).

V) Strategies for Addressing the Needs of Generation X and Generation Y**i) Strategies for Generation X**

1. Implement Flexible Work Policies: Organizations should implement flexible work policies, including remote work options and flexible scheduling, to accommodate Generation X's desire for work-life balance. This method facilitates the more efficient management of employees' professional and personal affairs (Twenge, 2010).

2. Offer Career Development Programs: Providing access to training, mentorship, and career advancement opportunities can help meet Generation X's expectations for professional growth. Organizations should invest in programs that support skill development and career progression (McCrindle, 2021).

3. Recognize Contributions: Implementing recognition programs and valuing the experience of Generation X employees can enhance job satisfaction and engagement. Acknowledging their achievements and leveraging their expertise contributes to a positive work environment (Schroth, 2019).

ii) Strategies for Generation Y

1. Promote Purpose and Values: Organizations should communicate their mission, values, and social responsibility initiatives to align with Millennials' desire for purposeful work. Engaging Millennials in projects that contribute to social and environmental causes can enhance their job satisfaction (Deloitte, 2023).

2. Facilitate Continuous Learning: Investing in training and development programs that support Millennials' need for career advancement and skill development is crucial. Organizations should provide resources for continuous learning and create pathways for career progression (Gallup, 2016).

3. Enhance Feedback Mechanisms: Establishing regular feedback and communication channels can help meet Millennials' preference for continuous feedback and transparent dialogue. Implementing performance review systems and creating opportunities for open communication are essential for this generation (Pew Research Center, 2019).

Conclusion In today's modern workplace, personnel belonging to Generation X and Generation Y bring with them a unique set of expectations, concerns, and requirements (Shams, G., Rehman, M. A., Samad, S., & Oikarinen, E. L., 2020). By gaining an awareness of these traits and addressing the specific requirements that they entail, organizations have the ability to cultivate a work atmosphere that is more inclusive and productive (Rawal, Y. S., & Singh, S., 2018). Employee engagement, contentment, and retention will all be improved through the implementation of methods that cater to the distinctive characteristics of each generation, which will eventually contribute to the effectiveness of the business.

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